

A Comparative Study of 2D Character Development in Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5

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Abstract:

This study compares the process of developing a basic 2D character with movement in four directions (up, down, left, right) across three popular game engines: Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5. Five participants, all unfamiliar with game engines, were tasked with implementing the movement system in each engine. The average time taken to complete the task was **42 minutes** in **Godot 4**, **67 minutes** in **Unity**, and **78 minutes** in **Unreal Engine 5**. Code complexity, development time, and available resources were evaluated. **Godot 4** proved to be the most efficient engine for 2D development, offering minimal code complexity and strong 2D-specific documentation. **Unity** required more time due to the verbosity of C# coding, though it benefited from an extensive support network. **Unreal Engine 5**, while still functional, took the longest time due to its focus on 3D, with fewer dedicated 2D resources. Overall, **Godot 4** emerged as the most suitable engine for beginner-level 2D development.

Keywords: 2D Game Development, Godot 4, Unity, Unreal Engine 5, Character Movement, Code Complexity

Introduction:

The popularity of 2D game development persists due to its simplicity and the relative ease with which new developers can learn the basics of game design. Game engines like Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5 provide powerful tools for creating both 2D and 3D games, but their performance in terms of ease of use, development time, and available resources varies. The purpose of this study is to compare the process of developing a 2D character capable of walking in four directions using these three engines. The research focuses on three key areas: code complexity, development time, and the availability of documentation and community resources. By doing so, the study offers insights into the most appropriate platform for 2D game development, particularly for those who are new to game engines.

Research Questions:

1. How does the complexity of the code for implementing 2D character movement compare across Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5?
2. How do the development time and ease of use differ for implementing basic 2D character mechanics in each engine?
3. What level of documentation and community support is available for 2D game development in each engine?

Literature Review:

The documentation provided by Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5 sheds light on the engines' functionalities, especially for beginners in 2D game development.

- **Godot 4:** Godot is known for its streamlined approach to 2D game development. GDScript, its native scripting language, is designed for simplicity, which is highlighted in the official documentation. The engine is widely praised for being beginner-friendly and well-suited for 2D projects (Godot Docs, 2023).
- **Unity:** Unity offers extensive documentation that covers both 2D and 3D development. Its scripting language, C#, is well-integrated with the engine but tends to be more verbose compared to GDScript. Unity's Asset Store and wealth of community tutorials provide substantial support for developers of all skill levels (Unity Docs, 2023).
- **Unreal Engine 5:** Unreal Engine's Paper2D system supports 2D development, but the engine is traditionally known for its 3D capabilities. Unreal's Blueprint system allows for visual scripting, which can simplify coding tasks, but the documentation and tutorials specific to 2D development are more limited compared to Godot and Unity (Unreal Engine Docs, 2023).

Methodology:

Five participants, all of whom were unfamiliar with game engines, were selected to test the development process in Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5. Each participant was tasked with implementing a 2D character that could move up, down, left, and right in a newly created 2D project. The following steps were taken for each engine:

1. **Engine Setup:** The latest versions of Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5 were installed, and new 2D projects were created in each engine.
2. **Character Movement Implementation:** A simple character capable of four-directional movement was developed using the default scripting systems for each engine:
 - **Godot 4:** Implemented using GDScript.
 - **Unity:** Implemented using C#.
 - **Unreal Engine 5:** Implemented using Blueprint visual scripting.
3. **Data Collection:**
 - The time taken to implement basic movement was recorded for each participant and averaged.
 - Code complexity was evaluated based on the length and clarity of the code required to achieve the movement.
 - The quality and availability of documentation and community resources were assessed.

Results:

Godot 4:

- **Average Development Time:** 42 minutes.
- **Code Complexity:** Low. GDScript's syntax is concise, and the engine's focus on 2D simplifies implementation.
- **Documentation and Support:** Strong. Godot offers well-documented 2D-specific tutorials, and its community, while smaller than Unity's, is dedicated and helpful.

Unity:

- **Average Development Time:** 67 minutes.
- **Code Complexity:** Moderate. C# requires more lines of code, but Unity's robust libraries and asset store make up for some of the complexity.
- **Documentation and Support:** Extensive. Unity has a large number of official and community-based tutorials and assets that provide strong support for 2D development.

Unreal Engine 5:

- **Average Development Time:** 78 minutes.
- **Code Complexity:** Low, thanks to Blueprint visual scripting, but the setup for 2D is more involved due to Unreal's heavy 3D focus.
- **Documentation and Support:** Limited. While Unreal has extensive 3D resources, its support for 2D development, specifically Paper2D, is not as robust as that of Godot or Unity.

Discussion:

1. How does the complexity of code for implementing 2D character movement compare across Godot 4, Unity, and Unreal Engine 5?

Godot 4 offers the simplest code structure. GDScript allows for rapid implementation with fewer lines of code, making it easy for beginners to understand. **Unity** requires more verbose coding in C#, although its libraries help manage some of the complexity. **Unreal Engine 5** simplifies coding with its visual Blueprint system, but setting up 2D projects takes longer and is less intuitive due to its 3D orientation.

2. How do the development time and ease of use differ for implementing basic 2D character mechanics in each engine?

Godot 4 is the most efficient, with an average development time of **42 minutes**, thanks to its native support for 2D game mechanics and simplified scripting. **Unity** takes longer, at **67 minutes**, primarily due to the complexity of C# and the need for more setup, but it benefits from a rich ecosystem of assets and support. **Unreal Engine 5** takes the longest at **78 minutes**. Despite its visual scripting, the engine's focus on 3D development means that 2D setup is more cumbersome.

3. What level of documentation and community support is available for 2D game development in each engine?

Unity provides the most comprehensive documentation and community resources, including a wide range of tutorials and plugins. **Godot 4** also has strong 2D-specific documentation, though its community is smaller. **Unreal Engine 5** has fewer 2D-

focused resources, and its Paper2D system is not as well-documented or supported as its 3D tools.

Conclusion:

For 2D character development, **Godot 4** proves to be the most efficient engine, offering a faster implementation time, simpler code, and well-documented support for 2D games. **Unity**, while more complex and requiring more time, provides a robust array of resources and flexibility for both 2D and 3D projects. **Unreal Engine 5**, though functional for 2D development, is less optimized for this purpose, with longer development times and fewer 2D-specific resources. For beginners or those focused on 2D projects, **Godot 4** is the recommended choice, while **Unity** is ideal for developers who require a balance between 2D and 3D development options.

References

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